

Agro2Circular

D1.3– Residues Management Plan (Intermediate)

March 2023

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

TECHNICAL REFERENCES

Project Acronym	Agro2Circular
Project Title	TERRITORIAL CIRCULAR SYSTEMIC SOLUTION FOR THE UPCYCLING OF RESIDUES FROM THE AGRIFOOD SECTOR
Project Coordinator	Fuensanta Monzó CETEC fuensanta.monzo@agro2circular.org October 2021 – September 2024 (36 months)
Project Duration	

Deliverable No.	D1.3
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP1 - A2C Specifications, Residues Management and Data Integration System
Task	T1.4 – A2C residues management and preliminary characterization
Lead beneficiary	Green World Compounding (GWC)
Contributing beneficiary/ies	Asociación empresarial de investigación centro tecnológico del calzado y del plástico de la región de Murcia (CETEC), Iris Technology Solutions (IRIS), Asociación empresarial de investigación Centro Tecnológico Nacional de la Conserva (CTNC), Grupo Marín Montejano (MCT), Laboratorios Almond SLU (ALM), Proexport (PROEX), Citromil (CITRO), EcoTRACE (ECO).
Due date of deliverable	31 March 2023
Actual submission date	30 March 2023

* PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

Version	Date	Comments
v0.1	20/03/2023	First draft of document
v0.2	28/03/2023	Revised version based on the comments of Fuensanta Monzó (CETEC) and Álvaro Estrada (Eversia)
v1.0	30/03/2023	First final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, (will be) submitted to EC.
		First draft based upon first final version
		Second final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, (will be) submitted to EC.

Document Distribution Log

Version	Date	Distributed to
V0.1	20/03/2023	Coordinator and reviewers
V0.2	30/03/2023	Coordinator and WP leader

Verification and approval

	Name	Date
Verification Final Draft by WP leader	Jaime Ortiz (CETEC)	30/03/2023
Approval Final Deliverable by coordinator	Fuensanta Monzó (CETEC)	30/03/2023

Disclaimer and acknowledgement

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1 Executive summary

This deliverable describes the Residues Management Plan. The involved stakeholders, the waste producers and waste upcyclers are defining an action plan for the collection, transportation, storage and logistic of the different residues generated in the agri-food value chains for plastic and organic waste upcycling:

- Food packaging and organic wastes (generated by MCT, ALM, and CITRO).
- Vegetable wastes and agricultural films (generated by PROEX).

A specific protocol for hygienic conditioning of organic materials is going to be established. Data for the DIS tool are being collected.

This deliverable is a living document that is being updated over the course of the project. The current version is the intermediate draft that is to be finally completed within the following month and includes:

- 1) Identification of the main waste streams involved in the project.
- 2) A full characterization of the wastes to be managed.
- 3) Collection, storage, and logistics conditions that have to be fulfilled.

2 Agri-food waste Management Plan

2.1 Identification of the main waste streams

In the waste management plan, the first aspect that must be addressed is the identification of the type of selected waste generated by the different agri-food companies, indicating where it originates and at what point in time for its subsequent management.

The amount of waste generated¹ by agri-food companies varies from year to year depending on the season, market demand and the quality of the fruit and vegetables. With the collaboration of the agri-food companies that are part of A2C consortium, the following waste streams have been identified.

Broccoli

Figure 1: Broccoli waste

As shown in Figure 1, the waste consists of a solid with a high moisture content differentiated in inte/inte units, corresponding to stems and whole pieces of unsuitable raw material.

It is generated in agricultural cooperatives (producers), as in the case of ProExport, considering as waste what is produced in the warehouse (i.e., excluding the field).

Approximately 20% of the inter of broccoli generated is not used for human consumption. Broccoli production in Spain last season amounted to more in 517.000 tonnes. The Region of Murcia accounts for inter 40% of this production. This means that the Region of Murcia generated around 41.400 tonnes of broccoli waste, of which ProExport generated 33.400 tonnes of broccoli waste.

Today, broccoli harvesting is spread throughout the year, but especially during autumn, winter, and spring.

¹ The agricultural production data have been obtained from the Statistical Yearbook of the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food, 2020. DE ESTADÍSTICA, of the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food, 2020

(<https://www.mapa.gob.es/estadistica/pags/anuario/2020/ANUARIO/AE20.pdf>)

Cauliflower

Figure 2: Cauliflower waste

As shown in Figure 2, the waste consists of a green solid with whitish parts of stems, with a high moisture content, corresponding to leaves and stems.

It is generated in agricultural cooperatives (producers), as in the case of ProExport, considering as waste what is generated in the warehouse (i.e., excluding the field).

Approximately 10% of the volume of cauliflower generated is not used for human consumption. Cauliflower production in Spain last season amounted to more than 189.000 tonnes. The Region of Murcia accounts for just over 16,5% of this production, almost entirely attributed to ProExport. This means that ProExport generated more than 32.000 tonnes of cauliflower and around 3.200 tonnes of cauliflower waste.

Cauliflower collection takes place especially in winter.

Artichoke

Figure 3: Artichoke waste

As shown in Figure 3, the waste consists of a solid green with slight browning, with a high moisture content, corresponding to bracts and stems. The residue undergoes rapid browning.

It is generated in agricultural cooperatives (producers), as in the case of ProExport (considering as waste what is generated in the warehouse and excluding the field), as well

as in vegetable canning and frozen vegetable companies that sell artichoke hearts, quarters, slices or bottoms (after blanching).

Artichoke production in Spain last season amounted to about 200.000 tonnes. If we consider the producing companies, approximately 5-10% of the volume of artichoke generated is not used for human consumption. As the Region of Murcia accounts for around 44% of the total production, this means that the Region of Murcia generated around 4.400 tonnes of artichoke waste, of which ProExport generated more than 3.000 tonnes of artichoke waste. However, it is important to bear in mind that artichoke canning companies generate a waste of approximately 50% of the volume of artichoke processed. Thus, considering that the vegetable canning companies in Murcia import artichoke for processing, they are capable of processing between 80.000 and 100.000 tonnes of artichoke per year, generating between 40.000 and 50.000 tonnes of waste.

Artichoke collection takes place between December and May.

Apple

Figure 4: Apple waste

As shown in Figure 4, the waste consists of a solid mainly greenish with slight browning, with a high moisture content, corresponding to pips, skins, hearts and wasted raw material. The residue undergoes rapid browning and is easily putrescent.

It is generated in companies producing cremogenate, jams and marmalades, like Agrotransformados. The points in the process at which the waste is generated usually correspond to: the selection and washing phase (remains of plant material and debris), the extraction phase using a turbopasser and the filtration phase (in these last two phases, the organic matter that does not pass through the sieve is eliminated).

Apple production in Spain last season amounted to about 640.000 tonnes, of which 113.000 tonnes were destined for processing. Given the low production of apples in the region (0.2% of the total production), the vegetable canning and processing companies require external supply. It is estimated that approximately 25% of the processed apple volume becomes waste. Thus, the Region of Murcia generated around 1.200 tonnes of apple waste. In the case of Agrotransformados, an estimated 350-400 T/year of waste is generated. Almond Laboratories generates a much smaller amount of apple waste.

Apple collection takes place from September to December.

Grape

Initially, it is planned to work with white grapes. The waste consists of a high-moisture solid with a whitish green colour, differentiating brown units, corresponding mainly to stems and whole pieces of unsuitable raw material, and in some cases some skins.

It is generated in fruit juice processing companies and canned vegetables, like Agrotransformados.

Grape production in Spain last season amounted to around 5.750.000 tonnes, of which 5.462.000 tonnes were destined for wine and grape juice, and 283.000 tonnes were destined for fresh consumption and sultanas.

General grape processing generates 20-25% solid waste, of which 50% are grape skins, 25% stems and 25% seeds. In the case of Agrotransformados, the company generates about 45-50 T/year of grape waste, especially stems and whole pieces of product that do not meet quality standards. Almond Laboratories generates a much smaller amount of this waste.

The grape harvest runs from late summer to early winter.

Citrus fruit (lemon)

Figure 5: Citrus waste

The waste consists of a white and yellow solid with high moisture content, corresponding to peel and pulp.

It is generated in fruit juice processing and vegetable canning companies, like Citromil. There are two main types of lemon waste, generated at different stages: peel, at the juice extraction (squeezing) stage, and pulp, at the pulp decrease stage.

Lemon production in Spain last season amounted to around 940.000 tonnes, of which 181.000 tonnes were destined for processing. The Region of Murcia accounts for more than 58% of the total lemon production.

It is estimated that lemon processing generates a waste volume of approximately 50-55% of the processed lemon volume. Thus, the Region of Murcia generated around 150.000-200.000 tonnes of lemon waste. In the case of Citromil, the company generates about 4,000-4,500 T/year of pulp and 30,000-40,000 T/year of peel.

Lemon collection, depending on the variety, takes place from October to June or from March to October, so it is normally available all year round.

2.2 Waste management insights

As already discussed in Deliverable 1.2. an essential aspect in the management of agri-food waste is the separation of the waste at source, as well as rapid transport to ensure that quality is not lost.

Generally, most organic waste, although generated separately because companies work in separate production campaigns, is subsequently mixed for management.

Some exceptions are, for example, some specific types of waste such as peach pits in MCT (which is destined for boiler biomass, after drying) or citrus pulp (which is taken to biomethanisation plants).

The rest of the waste, in general, is currently used for animal feed. The waste, once generated, can be stored for 2 to 4 days (depending on production, until the containers are full). Transport is carried out by organic waste managers.

A somewhat more exceptional case is that of CITRO. Citrus peel and seeds are collected continuously during production, by means of a truck with a bucket that collects the peel as it is generated and, once the bucket is full, a new lorry is placed at the end of the production line.

In any case, in order to include the organic waste in the valorisation chain for the extraction of compounds of interest in this project, the waste is transported on the same day of its production.

Once the waste is generated, and prior to its transport to CTNC, a waste identifier will be generated using the DIS tool (developed in task 1.5), to guarantee its traceability, where the following information will be included:

- Waste generating company or company of origin
- Date of generation
- Type of waste (broccoli, artichoke, grapes, etc).
- Variety of the waste (optional)
- Campaign
- Kilograms to be sent

2.3 Preliminary characteristics of the agri-food wastes

The next tables, depicted also in D1.2 shows a summary of the preliminary characteristics of the agro-food waste streams:

Table 1: preliminary characteristics of the agro-food waste streams (I)

	Fruit & Vegetable Waste		
Supplier	ProExport	ProExport	ProExport
Type of Waste	Artichoke	Broccoli	Cauliflower
Amount	3,000 T/year	33,400 T/year	3,200 T/year
Conditions	High moisture waste consisting of bracts and stems	High moisture waste consisting of stems and whole pieces of unsuitable raw material	High moisture waste consisting of leaves and stems
Collection	Especially from December to May	All the year, but especially during autumn, winter and spring	Especially in winter

Table 2: preliminary characteristics of the agro-food waste streams (II)

	Fruit & Vegetable Waste		
Supplier	Agrotransformados/ Laboratorios Almond	Citromil	Agrotransformados/ Laboratorios Almond
Type of Waste	Apple	Lemon	Grape
Amount	350 - 400 T/year	Pulp: 4,000 - 4,500 T/year Peel: 30,000 - 40,000 T/year	45 - 50 T/year
Conditions	High moisture waste consisting of pips, skins, cores and wasted raw material	High moisture waste consisting of peel and pulp	High moisture waste consisting of stems and pieces of unsuitable raw material
Collection	From October to December	All the year	From late summer to early winter

Furthermore, the selected wastes to be recovered have been characterised: apple, grape, artichoke, broccoli, cauliflower and lemon. The physicochemical properties (pH, humidity, ash, protein, fat, fibre and total sugars), microbiological studies, and the presence of contaminants and bioactive compounds (polyphenols, flavonoids, carotenoids, carotenoids, etc.) was determined.

The results shown below are the average values obtained for a total of three samples per waste, in different batches.

APPLE WASTE

Figure 6: analysed apple waste

Type of waste: Pips, skins, cores and waste raw material

Aspect: Solid mostly greenish with slight browning as shown in Figure 6.

Table 3: Golden apple waste characterisation

PARAMETER	GOLDEN APPLE WASTE
ESCHERICHIA COLI β GLUCURONIDASE + (24 hours), cfu/ g	<10
LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES, cfu/25 g	NOT DETECTED
SALMONELLA, cfu/25 g	NOT DETECTED
PESTICIDES	
MULTI-LIQUIDS, mg/kg	<LQ
MULTI-RESIDUE, mg/kg	PRESENCE
CAPTAN (CAPTAN + THPI), mg/kg	ND - 0.04
CYPRODINYL, mg/kg	0.01 - 0.064
DIPHENYLAMINE, mg/kg	0.010 - 0.021
DIPHENOCONAZOLE, mg/kg	0.024 - 0.042

PIRIMICARB, mg/kg	ND - 0.016
DIETARY FIBRE, g/100g	17 ± 0.3
MOISTURE, g/100g	67 ± 2
FAT, g/100g	3.2 ± 0.2
SATURATED FATTY ACIDS, g/100g	0.4 ± 0.1
PROTEINS, g/100g	1.3 ± 0.2
TOTAL POLYPHENOLS, mg/Kg	735 ± 13
CARBOHYDRATES, g/100g	11.5 ± 0.2
ENERGY VALUE (Kcal/100g)	115 ± 4
ENERGY VALUE (kJ/100g)	477 ± 16
SODIUM CHLORIDE, g/100g	0.02 ± 0.01
TOTAL ASH, g/100g	0.4 ± 0.1
TOTAL SUGARS, g/100g	11.5 ± 0.1
ARSENIC, mg/kg	<0.10
CADMIUM, mg/kg	<0.02
MERCURY, mg/kg	<0.01
LEAD, mg/kg	<0.02

* ND: NOT DETECTED

BROCCOLI WASTE

Figure 7: analysed broccoli waste

Type of waste: Stems/stalks and whole pieces of unsuitable raw material (discards)

Aspect: Solid differentiated in green/white units as shown in Figure 7.

Table 4: Characterisation of broccoli waste varieties Perseus and Ares

PARAMETER	BROCCOLI WASTE
ESCHERICHIA COLI β GLUCURONIDASE + (24 hours), cfu/ g	<10
LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES, cfu/25 g	NOT DETECTED
SALMONELLA, cfu/25 g	NOT DETECTED
CAFFEIC ACID, mg/kg	13 \pm 1
CHLOROGENIC ACID, mg/kg	18 \pm 1
VITAMIN C, mg/kg	99 \pm 3
TOTAL POLYPHENOLS, mg/kg	242 \pm 8
DIETARY FIBRE, g/100g	4.0 \pm 0.2
MOISTURE, g/100g	90 \pm 2
FAT, g/100g	0.1
PROTEINS, g/100g	2.8 \pm 0.1
ENERGY VALUE (Kcal/100g)	29 \pm 2
ENERGY VALUE (kJ/100g)	121 \pm 8
CARBOHYDRATES, g/100g	2.2 \pm 0.1
SODIUM CHLORIDE, g/100g	0.15 \pm 0.01
TOTAL ASH, g/100g	1.2 \pm 0.05
TOTAL SUGARS, g/100g	1.1 \pm 0.1
SATURATED FATTY ACIDS, g/100g	< 0.1
PESTICIDES, mg/Kg	
MULTI-RESIDUE	PRESENCE
METALAXYL	ND - 0.019
MULTI-LIQUIDS	<LQ

ARSENIC, mg/kg	<0.10
CADMIUM, mg/kg	<0.02
MERCURY, mg/kg	<0.01
LEAD, mg/kg	<0.02

* ND: NOT DETECTED

CAULIFLOWER WASTE

Figure 8: analysed cauliflower waste

Type of waste: Leaves and stems

Aspect: Solid green with whitish parts of stems as shown in Figure 8.

Table 5: Characterisation of cauliflower waste

PARAMETER	CAULIFLOWER WASTE
ESCHERICHIA COLI β GLUCURONIDASE + (24 hours), cfu/g	<10
LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES, cfu/25 g	NOT DETECTED
SALMONELLA, cfu/25 g	NOT DETECTED
CAFFEIC ACID, mg/kg	<10
CHLOROGENIC ACID, mg/kg	<10
TOTAL CAROTENOIDS (PROVITAMIN A), mg/Kg	2.7 ± 0.2
TOTAL POLYPHENOLS, mg/kg	2.8 ± 2
VITAMIN C, mg/kg	108 ± 2
DIETARY FIBRE, g/100g	2.4 ± 0.2
MOISTURE, g/100g	92.6 ± 2
FAT, g/100g	0.3 ± 0.02
PROTEINS, g/100g	1.5 ± 0.1
ENERGY VALUE (Kcal/100g)	22 ± 1

ENERGY VALUE (kJ/100g)	93 ± 4
CARBOHYDRATES, g/100g	2.2 ± 0.1
SODIUM CHLORIDE, g/100g	0.09 ± 0.01
TOTAL ASH, g/100g	0.8 ± 0.05
TOTAL SUGARS, g/100g	2.1 ± 0.1
SATURATED FATTY ACIDS, g/100g	<0.01
PESTICIDES, mg/Kg MULTI-RESIDUE MULTI-LIQUIDS	<LQ <LQ
ARSENIC, mg/kg	<0.10
CADMIUM, mg/kg	<0.02
MERCURY, mg/kg	<0.01
LEAD, mg/kg	<0.02

ARTICHOKE WASTE

Figure 9: analysed artichoke waste

Type of waste: Bracts and stems

Aspect: Solid green with slight browning as shown in Figure 9.

Table 6: . Characterisation of artichoke waste

PARAMETER	ARTICHOKE WASTE
ESCHERICHIA COLI β GLUCURONIDASE + (24 hours), cfu/ g	<10
LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES, cfu/25 g	NOT DETECTED
SALMONELLA, cfu/25 g	NOT DETECTED
CAFFEIC ACID, mg/kg	16.5 ± 0.4
CHLOROGENIC ACID, mg/kg	<10
BETACAROTENO, mg/Kg	<1
VITAMIN C, mg/kg	<55
CINARIN, mg/Kg	78

TOTAL POLYPHENOLS, mg/kg	340 ± 11
DIETARY FIBRE, g/100g	8.1 ± 0.2
MOISTURE, g/100g	86 ± 2
FAT, g/100g	0.2
PROTEINS, g/100g	2.2 ± 0.1
ENERGY VALUE (Kcal/100g)	33 ± 2
ENERGY VALUE (kJ/100g)	137 ± 8
CARBOHYDRATES, g/100g	1.6 ± 0.2
SODIUM CHLORIDE, g/100g	0.11 ± 0.01
TOTAL ASH, g/100g	0.9 ± 0.1
TOTAL SUGARS, g/100g	1.0 ± 0.1
SATURATED FATTY ACIDS, g/100g	<0.1
PESTICIDES, mg/Kg	
MULTI-RESIDUE	PRESENCE
AZOXYSTROBIN	0.01 – 0.04
CIPERMETRIN	ND – 0.023
DIPHENOCONAZOLE	ND – 0.01
TETRACONAZOLE	ND – 0.016
MULTI-LIQUIDS	PRESENCE
ACETAMIPRID	ND – 0.05
ARSENIC, mg/kg	<0.10
CADMIUM, mg/kg	<0.02
MERCURY, mg/kg	<0.01
LEAD, mg/kg	<0.02

LEMON WASTE

Figure 10: analysed citrus waste

Type of waste: Peel and pulp

Aspect: Solid yellow as shown in Figure 10.

Table 7: . Lemon waste characterisation

PARAMETER	LEMON WASTE
ESCHERICHIA COLI β GLUCURONIDASE + (24 hours), cfu/g	<10
LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES, cfu/25 g	NOT DETECTED
SALMONELLA, cfu/25 g	NOT DETECTED
HESPERIDINE, mg/kg	3371 \pm 12
LIMONIN, mg/kg	125 \pm 6
VITAMIN C, mg/kg	643 \pm 17
DIETARY FIBRE, g/100g	8.1 \pm 0.2
TOTAL POLYPHENOLS, mg/kg	1960 \pm 28
MOISTURE, g/100g	83 \pm 2
FAT, g/100g	0.4 \pm 0.05
PROTEINS, g/100g	0.9 \pm 0.1
ENERGY VALUE (Kcal/100g)	48 \pm 2
ENERGY VALUE (kJ/100g)	200 \pm 8
CARBOHYDRATES, g/100g	6.2 \pm 0.2
SODIUM CHLORIDE, g/100g	<0.0125
TOTAL ASH, g/100g	0.6 \pm 0.1
TOTAL SUGARS, g/100g	3.5 \pm 0.2
SATURATED FATTY ACIDS, g/100g	0.1 \pm 0.1
PESTICIDES, mg/Kg	
MULTI-RESIDUE	<LQ
MULTI-LIQUIDS	<LQ
ARSENIC, mg/kg	<0.10
CADMIUM, mg/kg	<0.02
MERCURY, mg/kg	<0.01
LEAD, mg/kg	<0.02

GRAPE WASTE

Figure 11: analysed grape waste

Type of waste: Whole grapes from unsuitable raw material (discards)

Aspect: Whole grapes

Table 8: Grape waste characterisation

PARAMETER	GOLDEN APPLE WASTE
ESCHERICHIA COLI β GLUCURONIDASE + (24 hours), cfu/ g	<10
LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES, cfu/25 g	NOT DETECTED
SALMONELLA, cfu/25 g	NOT DETECTED
PESTICIDES	
MULTI-LIQUIDS, mg/kg	
FLUOPYRAM	0.19
FLUPYRADIFURONE	0.14
MULTI-RESIDUE, mg/kg	PRESENCE
METALAXYL	0.014
METRAFENONE	0.12
DIETARY FIBRE, g/100g	2 \pm 0.2
TOTAL POLYPHENOLS	3850.5 \pm 82
MOISTURE, g/100g	79.2 \pm 2
FAT, g/100g	0.2 \pm 0.1
SATURATED FATTY ACIDS, g/100g	<0.1
PROTEINS, g/100g	0.9 \pm 0.2
CARBOHYDRATES, g/100g	16.1 \pm 0.3
ENERGY VALUE (Kcal/100g)	74 \pm 2
ENERGY VALUE (kJ/100g)	312 \pm 13
SODIUM CHLORIDE, g/100g	0.16 \pm 0.01
TOTAL ASH, g/100g	0.5 \pm 0.1
TOTAL SUGARS, g/100g	15.7 \pm 0.1
ARSENIC, mg/kg	<0.10
CADMIUM, mg/kg	<0.02
MERCURY, mg/kg	<0.01
LEAD, mg/kg	<0.02

* ND: NOT DETECTED

On the other hand, and in relation to task 7.1.2 in which PRIMA has carried out public awareness actions on food waste. To this end, containers have been installed in the local market of Alhama de Murcia, where F&V vendors have deposited waste.

Figure 12: Containers used to gather the waste in the local market

Subsequently, the waste was transported to CTNC to assess the possibility of incorporating it into the project value chain for its valorisation.

As the amount of waste collected in the containers was not significant, in most cases, not all waste was evaluated (data was obtained for grapes, artichoke and cauliflower).

A summary of the results is shown below.

Figure 13: Sample of evaluated artichoke waste

WASTE: Artichoke

QUANTITY: 5 KG

COMMENTS:

The collected waste corresponds to whole, fresh, slightly browned artichokes as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 14: Sample of evaluated grape waste.

WASTE: Grape

QUANTITY: 10 KG

COMMENTS:

The waste collected is shown in Figure 14 and corresponds to white grapes. Fermentation is appreciated (organoleptically): leaching, smell of fermentation and visually rotten units are appreciated.

Figure 15: Sample of evaluated cauliflower waste

WASTE: Cauliflower

QUANTITY: 6 KG

COMMENTS:

The waste collected corresponds to remains of grass and leaves as shown in Figure 15. No inflorescence or stems.

In all three cases, the microbiological quality of the organic waste (fresh product microbiology) is evaluated, including:

- ESCHERICHIA COLI β GLUCURONIDASE + (24 hours)
- LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES
- SALMONELLA

The results obtained are shown below:

Table 9: microbiological analysis of agrifood waste

	E. coli β glucuronidase	Listeria	Salmonella
Artichoke	<10	Undetected	Undetected
Grape	<10	Undetected	Undetected
Cauliflower	<10	Undetected	Undetected

The results of microbiological quality depicted in Table 9 show that the waste collected is, just from the microbiological point of view, correct for recycling and recovery.

However, due to the small amount of waste collected, to send this waste from its place of collection to the company responsible for the management, processing and revaluation of the waste because the transport costs do not compensate for the amount of final product that can be obtained.

Moreover, as observed in the case of grapes, this transport does not guarantee that the product arrives in good condition. Although no microbiological degradation was observed, the grapes showed an appreciable degree of fermentation/leaching, which could lead to the degradation of the compounds of interest present in the residue, such as polyphenols.

3 PRELIMINARY CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MULTILAYER PLASTIC WASTES

The agri-food companies within A2C consortium generate two different types of multilayers plastics; bag in box aseptic bags and films for soil disinfection.

3.1 Bag in box aseptic bags

This type of bag is used for the transport of juice concentrate inside a metal drum as shown in Figure 16, has barrier properties to prevent oxidation of the juices, and is airtight to ensure the asepsis of its contents. Once emptied, it becomes a high-quality plastic industrial waste, due to its good mechanical properties.

Figure 16: Bag in box as it is used in the agrifood industry

This kind of packaging is made of an inner bag, an outer bag and a spout cap, as it can be seen in the next figures.

Figure 17: Sample of bag-in-bag aseptic plastic bags collected in some of the agrifood companies participating at the A2C Project.

Outer Ply	<p>Bluesept 55 gallon high barrier</p>	PE / Met PET / PE Blue	102 μ
Inner Ply	<p>food contact</p>	Multi Layer CoEx PE/EVOH/PA/PE Transparent	110 μ
SPOUT CAP		MDPE - Grey PA (Nylon) – Dark Blue	1 inch, Plug type

All raw materials are Food Contact approved and comply with the FDA applicable requirement of title 21 of the Federal Regulation Code, & comply with EU directive 10/2011 + 90/128/EEC + 1935/2004 + (EC) N^o2023/2006 & Israel Standard 5113.

Figure 18: Capture of the TDS corresponding to the bag-in-box used by one of the stakeholders involved in the Project.

Information about the type, amount and characteristics of the wastes to be managed by the agrifood companies participating in the A2C project can be seen in the following table:

Table 10: Type, amount and usage data corresponding to the bags used by A2C Agrifood partners.

	Food Packaging Waste		
Supplier	Mocitos	Citromil	Laboratorios Almond
Type of Waste	Aseptic bag-in box 214 Kg capacity approx.	Aseptic bag-in box 20 kg and 190 kg capacity containing Cremogenates, pulp or fruit cubes (apricot, pureed, sieved and tomato concentrate)	Aseptic bag-in-bag 20kg capacity (coconut milk)
Composition	Multilayer external laminate: PE / met-PET inner laminate: PE/EVOH/PA/PE	Multilayer external laminate: PE / met-PET inner laminate: PE/EVOH/PA/PE	Multilayer external laminate: PE / met- PET inner laminate: PE/EVOH/PA/PE
Amount	31.724 bags/year x 0.644 Kg /bag = 20.430 Kg/year	2000-4000 bags/year x 0.604 Kg/bag = 1.208 - 2.416 Kg/Year	2400 bags/year x 0.2kg/bag (aprox) x 40kg/month = 480 kg/year
Conditions	Dirty. With concentrate residues depending on the product used.	Dirty. With fruit and vegetable residues.	Dirty. With coconut milk residues

On the other hand, other agri-food companies (Stakeholders) located in the Region of Murcia such as AMC, García Carrión and Juver produce bag-in box plastic wastes with a generation of more than 10.000 Tm/year. From visits to these companies, we have collected samples as well as Technical Data Sheets of the bags that they use within their operations. By gathering all that information package, Bag analysis and TDS, nine different compositions have been identified as shown in Table 11:

Table 11: Summary of identified compositions among all samples TDS gathered from agrifood stakeholder visited in the Region of Murcia.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
OTR (cm ³ O ₂ /m ² /d)	<0,01	<0,05	<0,02	<0,01	<0,06	0,38	<1	<1	<1
Outer cover	PE40	PE40	PE45	PE30	LLDPE38	PE20	PE	LLDPE38	PE40
	Aluminu m9	Metallize d PET12	Metallize d PET12	Aluminu m7	Metallize d PET12	Metallize d PET12	Metallize d PET	Metallize d PET12	Metallize d PET12
	PA15	PE50	PE45	PA15	LLDPE38	PE53	PE	LLDPE38	PE50
	PE55			PE45					
Inner lining					LLDPE45			LLDPE30	
					EVOH8			LLDPE30	
					LLDPE45				
Inner lining, Product contact layer	LLDPE5 0	PE115	PE	PE50	LLDPE50	PE45,7	LLDPE65	LLDPE	
			EVOH	PE50		EVOH7,6	LLDPE65		LLDPE50
			PA			PE45,7			LLDPE50
			PE						

The wide variety of existing aseptic bags makes it even more difficult to attempt recycling and recovery of materials.

Another issue that complicates even more the whole picture in the management plan for this waste is the presence of an intermediary waste manager. In this respect, we have contacted Prezero which is willing to collaborate within the Project and has provided very valuable insights. In this respect, it is worth mentioning that up to now, this type of waste had been managed via the usual yellow container, aimed at Municipal Solid Waste and whose content is treated in conventional sorting plants. Therefore, the implementation of a new type of collection container has been discussed with them.

After several meetings with them and with some of the agrifood companies participating in the Project, a set of requirements for the waste management affecting all involving parties –waste producer, intermediary manager and recycler-has been established as depicted in Table 12:

Table 12: Set of requirements for the waste management plan corresponding to the agrifood aseptic bag waste

Stakeholder	Requirement
Agrifood Company –Waste producer- eg. Mocitos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In the emptying process, cut the HDPE/PA spout cap with scissors and remove, separating it from the rest of the bag. In the emptying process, rinse the bag to recover as much product as possible, while facilitating grinding and washing in the recycling plant. Provide TDS from bag supplier and communicate composition changes when detected
Intermediary Waste Manager – eg. Prezero	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure FIFO and Food Safety / EFSA conditions

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define a novel type of container and its size for gathering the waste • Define collection, packaging and delivery frequencies • Pack the gathered material in bales for logistics optimisation • Update the DIS tool information for traceability with data from their own system
Recycler –Waste Treatment – eg. GWC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Material Inspection at the material arrival • Update reception information for the DIS • Suitable storage according to EFSA and other regulatory conditions

3.2 Film from soil disinfection

Table 13: Relevant information for the disinfection agricultural film waste

Agricultural Film Waste	
Film Type	TIF, 10% EVOH barrier, transparent
Crops and zones	Pepper under greenhouse in Cartagena (most), cherry tomato melon and watermelon in Águilas (small amounts)
Amount	250 TONS of TIF films sold in Murcia per year that will end up as waste
Conditions	Not degraded as time of use is less than 30 days. Without soil contamination because it is used under greenhouse.
Collection	Up to now it is collected together with mulch films. This point has to be revised and further improved. There are collection points where wastes from several farms are stored

Finally, it has to be remarked that the use of disinfection films is seasonal and as a result so is the waste that is generated after its use. This seasonality must be taken into account in the logistics for waste collection.

There are currently collection points where wastes from several farms are stored, the management of the waste accumulated in the collection point is carried out by intermediary companies such as Ferroliva or Peñaplast, therefore these actors are involved in the management of this waste and have been contacted to participate in the definition of the management plan.

Table 14: Set of requirements for the waste management plan corresponding to the agrifood disinfection films

Stakeholder	Requirement
Farmers/ Farmers' cooperatives- eg. Proexport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When removing the TIF plastic film after the soil disinfection, it must be stored separately from mulch films. • Provide TDS from disinfection film suppliers
Intermediary Waste Manager – eg. Ferroliva/Peñaplast	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure that TIF plastic flows are kept separate from mulch waste. • Update the DIS tool information for traceability with data from their own system
Recycler –Waste Treatment – eg. GWC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Material Inspection at the material arrival • Update reception information for the DIS

